

УДК 140.8; 32

NEW WORLD ORDER OR THE “THREE WHALES” CONCEPT

НОВЫЙ МИРОВОЙ ПОРЯДОК ИЛИ КОНЦЕПЦИЯ «ТРЕХ КИТОВ»

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Abstract. This article reveals the essence of the main trends of the new world order and the factors of human development, as well as the transition to new economic circumstances characterized by the “three whales” concept: poverty, unemployment and disease. The author also pays attention to the role of investment in the formation of a new world order, new methods for calculating macroeconomic and other indicators and global problems that impede further development.

Аннотация. В этой статье раскрывается сущность основных тенденций нового мирового порядка и факторов человеческого развития, а также переход к новым экономическим условиям, характеризуемым концепцией «трех китов»: нищета, безработица и болезни. Автор также обращает внимание на роль инвестиций в формирование нового мирового порядка, новые методы расчета макроэкономических и других показателей и глобальных проблем, которые препятствуют дальнейшему развитию.

Keywords: world order, politics, economics, technology, sociology, ecology, poverty, unemployment, diseases, trends, security, new economic system, model, competition, human values, “three whales”.

Ключевые слова: мировой порядок, политика, экономика, технология, социология, экология, бедность, безработица, болезни, тенденции, безопасность, новая экономическая система, модель, конкуренция, человеческие ценности, «три кита».

Today the world has changed beyond recognition, it has reached the level of development that previously was impossible to imagine. The competitive struggle is intensifying in all areas and given that such advanced countries like the US, Russia, China, Japan, Germany, etc. have a powerful economic and military potential, it is difficult to predict which country will become a global power. In this regard, the main task is to save the world from nuclear danger.

Over the past hundred years on the world order has changed three times. First time, after the First World War. Second, the end of the Second World War and the formation of the socialist camp. The third, the collapse of the USSR.

In the modern world, the principles of globalization primarily affect the vital interests of the world’s population and require a more qualitative approach in managing this process. In this regard,

world efforts should be aimed at the effective solution of numerous regional and global problems of human development.

The essence of the new world order is characterized by the following trends: the strengthening of structural changes in the state and social arrangement of individual countries; transition to a new economy; the formation of a civilized man. However, even at this stage, there are such constraining factors as poverty, disease and unemployment. Despite billions of dollars spent to this triad all over the world, living conditions in poor countries do not improve. For example, at present, from 8 to 15% of people do not have a permanent job from the total number of the world's able-bodied population. The number of hungry people is more than 1 billion. The incidence of cancer, diabetes also does not decrease, but on the contrary increases.

We decided to combine all these factors conditionally into "three whales". Over the past hundred years, medicine has made a powerful leap, and it seems that for most diseases, even if a medicine is not found, the cause is known. However, there are a number of diseases that still pose science in a dead end, and the solution of the mystery of them, as the great Avicenna wrote in his time, is also the progress of mankind.

Considering that the concept of "three whales" is the main prerogative of the state, the Republic of Uzbekistan has adopted a socially-oriented model of the economy since gaining the independence and annually allocates about 60% of its budget for the development of the social sphere. Annually about one million new jobs are created in the republic.

The formation of a new world order is based on education, health, environmental development, provision of portable water, employment of the population, preservation of peace and other factors. In this regard, an integrated approach is needed during the adopting strategies in these areas.

The model of the new world order has long attracted the attention of many scientists and specialists. However, a model that can cover all aspects of the world order has not been created. Those countries that seek to create a model of a new world order, unfortunately, do not have the experience and a complete picture of the attributes of a universal civilization. In developing such a model, attention should be paid primarily to the economy (investment, innovative technologies), environmental security, peace and tranquility. In addition, the model of the new world order, first of all, should meet the principle of peaceful coexistence of all states and peoples.

The model of a new world order should not be politicized, but should contribute to solving the social and economic problems of the development of the world economy. It's no secret that over the past 10-15 years even the leading countries of the world (G7 and G20) are weakened economically, since they invest huge resources in the military sphere, which today is the first characteristic of the world order.

The second distinguishing feature of our time is environmental safety. Yearly industrial and other emissions polluting the drinking water lead to the emergence of various diseases.

The third trend is the transfer of industrial capacities to developing countries.

The fourth feature is the integration of capital and production. It is known that capital which was not invested in production considered to be a "dead". Therefore, their integration stimulates the development of the production process.

At present, the developed countries have accumulated a huge scale of foreign investment. For example, the US - 3 trillion 450 billion dollars, the UK - 2 trillion 300 billion, France - 1 trillion 120 billion. In a market environment, the restructuring of public debt is an important condition for stabilizing the economy, for example, for the US this appears to be a serious problem, where the national debt exceeds the GDP.

The fifth trend is the rational use of resources. According to some data, the amount of the world's natural resources is about 610-620 trillion dollars. This amount of the world wealth can feed only 30 billion of people and no more. If every 14 years the population will grow by 1 billion, then in the next 325 years, it will reach the figure of 30 billion, in this regard the globalization of human resources is becoming to be one of the most serious problem.

The sixth feature is a technological renovation of production and the robotization of many processes. The world is on the verge of 6-7 technological way, that is “nanotechnology”. However, we should remember that it is impossible to live without world market, which in our view, is a postulate of the new world order, since the implementation of mutually complementary products and equal relations in competition, and the mutually beneficial position of all participants in the world market can be reached.

The new world order should radically change the life of the population of the globe, provide employment and preserve health. In this direction, purposeful work is carried out under the auspices of the United Nations, the World Bank, OECD and other authoritative organizations, which allocate huge amount of resources for this. With regard to the management of this process, different points of view on the structural, institutional and hierarchical construction of a new order are expressed, but we still want to share our vision.

In our opinion, the only organization that can regulate the world order is the UN, except of financing where the World Bank will play the main role.

Another important issue is when exactly the new world order will enter into the force? Analysis of interpretations and approaches shows that there is still no clarity in this direction, and if we proceed from the concept of “three whales”, the process will be lengthy. The solution of tendentious problems will also take a long time.

Currently, the system of national reports is used in preparation of works on the analysis of macroeconomic indicators associated with the dynamics of development of individual states. The formation of new world order is important to link with a wide range of calculations. In this regard, we propose to use the PETSE system (politics-economics-technology-sociology-ecology). Such a system will cover all aspects of world civilization.

The creation of the world order is also closely related to such global problems as:

- development of world business;
- transition to nanotechnologies;
- profound reform of healthcare and education;
- further strengthening of integration;
- food security;
- maintaining stable military and defense power, curbing the arms race;
- achievement of equality of peoples;
- investment in global projects;
- assistance to the socio-economic and technological development of poor countries;
- development of the information society.

The author of this article does not pretend to exhaustive coverage of all relevant problems of development and management of the new world order, he made only an attempt to carry out the analysis in the theoretical and practical terms in this field. He got acquainted with the works and articles of major scientists and specialists in the field of international relations and the world order, such as A. Battler, F. Fukuyama, A. Neklessa, N. Zagladin, A. Bekturov, P. Tsygankov, E.Di Nolfo, I. Wallerstein, M. Khrustalev. These works generalize a significant path of development of the world order and give their vision of how it will be formed in the future.

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*Работа поступила
в редакцию 06.07.2017 г.*

*Принята к публикации
10.07.2017 г.*

Cite as (APA):

Zainutdinov, Sh. (2017). New world order or the “Three whales” concept. *Bulletin of Science and Practice*, (8), 275-278

Ссылка для цитирования:

Zainutdinov Sh. New world order or the “Three whales” concept // Бюллетень науки и практики. Электрон. журн. 2017. №8 (21). С. 275-278. Режим доступа: <http://www.bulletennauki.com/zainutdinov-1> (дата обращения 15.08.2017).